

Investigating the Interplay Between Cervical Spine Sagittal Balance and Lower Back Pain Using Computational Biomechanics and Biomedical Imaging

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Abstract

Understanding cervical sagittal balance has emerged as a crucial diagnostic criterion due to the relationship between disability, horizontalization of the gaze, and multiple neuropathologies. While numerous studies have investigated the entire cervical complex, the distinctive morphology, and biomechanics of the first two cervical vertebrae necessitate further analysis regarding weight distribution and behavior in relation to typical vertebrae. To investigate this phenomenon, we developed a morphologically simplified finite element model of the C1-C5 segment to examine the stresses and strains experienced by the cervical spine under multi-modal loading, to simulate the influence of the upper cervical region on the other cervical vertebrae spanning from C1 to C5. Our preliminary results demonstrate the effects of spine position on the distribution of stresses and strains in the intervertebral discs which may play a key role in the causation of pathological cervical balance. Emulating the superior and anterior compression, the effective stress trend was shown in the postero-superior and the deformation in C1-C2-C3 and antero-inferior for C4-C5. Based on these findings, it can be compared with various degenerative pathophysiological processes of the cervical spine. This novel approach opens up new perspectives for investigating the interplay between cervical sagittal balance and lower back pain.

Keywords: Upper Cervical, Finite Element, Sagittal Balance, Biomechanics, Forward Head Posture.

1 Introduction

1.1 Cervical Sagittal Balance

The sagittal profile to achieve horizontal vision is important in all ages, and the deterioration of spinal alignment due to aging is compensated by the supportive function of the spine, pelvis and lower extremities to maintain the horizontal gaze (Hasegawa et al., 2017). The sagittal balance of the cervical spine is correlated with disability and neck pain when the forward head posture is present due to a smaller craniovertebral angle considered less than 48-50° (Ruivo et al., 2014). Conversely, the craniovertebral angle is often used for posture measurements, but it is rarely analysed with the general radiological parameters of sagittal balance (Le Huec et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the behavior of the cervical spine defines the position because it is part of the sagittal balance system that involves the equilibrium of the body through physiological alignment of the spine in the most efficient manner via muscular forces (Le Huec et al., 2019). To fully understand the effects of the cervical spine alignment on the thoracolumbar spine it is important to understand the underlying biomechanics and interplay between cervical and lumbar spine biomechanics. Several studies have reported that the cervical sagittal balance is related to degenerative cervical spondylolisthesis. (Paholpak, 2017; Wang et al., 2021) lumbar pain (Arima, 2021), scoliosis (Obeid et al., 2015), pelvis position (Ferrero et al., 2021), muscle degeneration (Tamai et al., 2018), risk of postoperative sagittal spinal pelvic malalignment (Passias, 2015), global spinal alignment, and horizontal gaze (Diebo et al., 2016) and amongst others. To establish a connection between these pathologies and cervical sagittal balance, it is crucial to comprehend the effects starting from the fundamental level and progressing towards a comprehensive understanding of its biotensegric mechanism. This mechanism explores the morphological complexity of the cervical spine's architecture through its geometry, recognizing it as an energy-efficient mechanism (Scarr, 2020). However, despite the fact that cervical sagittal balance has been shown to be related to a wide variety of pathophysiological processes, it has not been investigated in depth using

the finite element method.

1.2 Biomechanics

In order to understand the cervical spine behavior it is important to recognize that the forward head posture moves the center of the body mass forward (Kim, 2022) through the particular anatomy and biomechanics of C1-C2 comprising approximately 40% of the total cervical flexion and 60% of the total cervical rotation (Frankel, 2021, Camp, 2016). Additionally, the complexity of the upper cervical region is not limited by mechanical parameters alone, it also affects the central nervous system. The head-forward individuals exhibited abnormal sensorimotor control and autonomic nervous system dysfunction compared to those with normal head alignment (Moustafa et al., 2020, Khan et al., 2020). In surgical practice, it is critical to understand that the biomechanics of the cervical spine plays an important role in maintaining correct head position after corrective surgeries of the thoracic spine (Cecchinato et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2022) and in the design of physical rehabilitation programmes. Considering the above, it is essential to understand the relationship between the stresses and strains that develop in the spinal components arising from cervical sagittal imbalance and how this contributes to pain in the lumbar spine region.

1.3 Finite Element Model of the Cervical Spine

Computer models are powerful tools to analyze the biomechanics of the human body (Crawford et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2014). The interpretation of the cervical sagittal balance effects on other spinal elements can be analyzed meticulously by calculating the stresses and strains that are produced in vertebrae, intervertebral disks, ligaments, etc. Furthermore, the joints and mechanical components of the upper cervical spine are complex and difficult to understand conventionally. Here, we used FEBio to develop a morphologically simplified model of the C1-C5 spine (Maas et al., 2012). Modeling of the cervical lordosis has been shown to be closely modeled with a circle (Harrison et al., 2004), so it is worth starting with basic geometric shapes for a simplified model of the cervical spine. The aim of this project was to develop a simple finite element model of the C1-C5 spine segment to predict the stresses and strains that develop in the cervical spine under multi-modal loading and inform future development of anatomically accurate and biofidelic models.

Figure 1 Boundary condition and Prescribed displacement of the finite element model of the C1-C5 sagittal cervical balance

2 Methods

Computational modeling has been used to simulate the influence of the upper cervical spine with respect to the other cervical vertebrae from C1 to C5. This was achieved by developing a morphologically simplified finite element model of the C1-C5 spine in FEBio Studio 2.1.2 (www.febio.org). A review of the literature provided information on the essential components that should be incorporated into the basic modeling of the cervical spine, including the vertebral bodies, ligaments, and intervertebral discs. In this case, simple geometric elements have been used to emulate the form and function of these components.

2.3 Finite Element Modelling

The cervical spine geometry was discretized using a 8-node hexahedral mesh. An 8-node hexahedral mesh was used as it provides excellent balance between computational accuracy, cost, and geometrical accuracy. Hexahedral elements are also more robust against element locking compared to tetrahedral elements. (Tadepalli et al., 2011) Contact interaction properties were assigned using Facet-to-Facet parameters to the superior and inferior endplate emulating the linking between endplate and intervertebral disc (IVD) surfaces. Four ligaments were modelled representing Posterior Longitudinal Ligaments and Four ligaments representing Anterior Longitudinal Ligaments.

2.4 Material properties

The vertebrae were modelled as an isotropic linear elastic material with a Young's modulus (E) = 17 GPa and Poisson's ratio = 0.3. The IVDs were modelled as neo-Hookean materials with a Young's modulus = 1.2 MPa and Poisson's ratio = 0.4. Ligaments were modelled as linear springs with $E = 2$ MPa.

2.3 Boundary conditions

In order to emulate a simple cervical spine model, a fixed boundary condition was applied to the bottom vertebrae (C5). **Figure 1** A prescribed displacement of 0.7 mm in the negative Z-direction was applied to C1 to simulate compression of the spine. A second simulation was performed simulating a 2 mm lateral displacement of C1. Finally, combined compression and lateral displacement of C1 was simulated.

Figure 2 Effective strain a displacement (Horn et al.), b displacement (y-), c displacement (z-y) of the finite element model of the C1-C5 sagittal cervical spine element model of the C1-C5 sagittal cervical spine.

3 Results

Once the model was developed the Effective stress and Effective Lagrange strain were predicted under three different loading conditions. First *compression only*, then *forward displacement only* and finally *combined compression-forward displacement*. In the top displacement (Compression) the stress distributed throughout the spine is slightly reflected in the vertebral bodies with but more intensely in the ligamentous insertions. Whereas strain is more pronounced in the IVDs, especially in the outer circumference. For the forward displacement case that are emulating the forward head position; the stress is distributed in the ligamentous insertion of the lower edge of C1 vertebrae and the upper edge of C2 vertebrae. The same is repeated for the lower edge of C4 vertebrae and upper edge of C5. The strain is observed attenuated in the IVDs of C1-C2 and C4-C5 and a minuscule deformation in the IVDs C2-C3 and C3-C4. After testing the effect separately, the analyze of both effects was performed at the same time, which would be the emulation of the C1-C2 articulation compressing and forward. Where the stress is pronounced in the posterior-inferior ligamentous insertion of C1, the complete posterior block of C2 and the posterior-superior ligamentous insertion of C3. In the lower part, the postero-inferior ligamentous insertion of C3 is detailed, the complete anterior block of C4 and a moderate part in anterior C5. Analyzing the figure of combined loads can be seen how stress and deformation are higher under a combined compression and forward displacement. This can provide information on the pathophysiological processes that lead to a process of wear due to microtraumas that can develop over time. This simplified model serves as a preliminary investigation of our hypothesis with further investigations planned with anatomically accurate FE models.

4 Conclusions

The simple finite element of the cervical spine produced general results on how multimodal loading might affect adjacent vertebrae. Emulating superior and anterior compression, the effective strain trend was shown in the postero-superior and the deformation in C1-C2-C3 and antero-inferior for C4-C5. Based on these findings, it can be compared with various degenerative pathophysiological processes of the cervical spine using different machine/vision imaging according to the type of pathophysiology. In addition, it can be predicted how the intervertebral discs deform in response to the anterior displacement of the upper segment. In this case, it is representing the upper cervical in the forward head posture position. This is a preliminary work where C1-C5 was analyzed to obtain information about its behavior and to be able to analyze it in the future with more precision. The model will be expanded to include the facet structure that is a load transmitter, the spinous processes that contact the stronger posterior ligaments, and the absence of C6-C7 for comprehensive analysis. Low back pain is one of the highest rates of disability and this model will provide us with new information that can be used to understand the biomechanical phenomenon that afflicts the lumbar spine and adjacent structures.

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